

DIALOGUE MATHEMATICS JOURNAL WRITING AND ITS IMPLICATION IN IMPROVING THE CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS IN DISTANCE EDUCATION

JOVEN D. CAPALAD¹

DELON A. CHING²

joven.capalad@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-9589-5278¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

San Pablo City Integrated High School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Comprehension plays a big role in understanding math and by using reflective journals, students can put their thoughts into writing and think critically. This study aimed to identify the student's perception of the use of dialogue Mathematics journal concerning their critical thinking skills. The study used descriptive and correlational methods in conducting the study which allowed the researcher to relate the students' perception of the use and utilization of the dialogue Mathematics journal to their critical thinking skills. A total of 250 students who took the modular distance learning modality this school year 2020-2021, were exposed to the process of using dialogue journal, after which were trimmed down by randomly selecting 30 participants to answer the survey and the critical thinking assessment. The use of descriptive analysis on the students' perception of the level of satisfaction in using the journal resulted from a satisfactory level under the phases of reflection, the content of reflection, and time of reflection, which implies that students are satisfied to use and utilize the process of journaling to enhance their thinking skills. Furthermore, the test of correlation shows that there is a positive relationship between their perception and their critical thinking which included Evaluating and Forming Arguments (Structure). Moreover, the result posted a significant improvement on Analyzing, Synthesizing, and Forming Arguments (Validity). This implies that not all factors under critical thinking are affected in using the dialogue journal. Thus, this study recommends including a dialogue journal as a supplemental activity to students as it showed positive effects on some aspects of Critical thinking.

Keywords: Critical Thinking, Dialogue Mathematics Journal, Journal Writing